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Methodological subversions in the absence of archives

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a methodological contribution around how the history of a sector can be researched when the records of the past have either not been maintained or erased. Set against the backdrop of Vietnam's colonial history and experiences of political turmoil, we had to overcome this challenge creatively, understanding what made sense for that context, what could be asked, and how to collect data when it was not possible due to (auto)censorship or absence of archives. We developed two alternative methods of inquiry: mobilising objects to discuss stories that otherwise would be censored, which we refer to as an object-oriented method, and an art-based method, based on critical fabulations. We explain the challenges of using traditional business history methods in this context, present the process of developing these two novel methods through empirical accounts, and finally discuss the ethical implications and limitations researchers might face in their application.

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1. Introduction

This paper makes a methodological contribution to the field of business history by drawing on theories of memory, relational-materiality and critical fabulations, and applying them empirically to the craft sector in Vietnam. During our fieldwork, we encountered an absence of archives, both in terms of written materials and records. This raised a series of questions and challenges for us as researchers, which underpin this paper. These include: How can we research the history of a sector, when the record of the past has either not been maintained or deliberately erased? What alternative strategies are available when both oral history and rhetorical history have proven to be problematic? What accountability does a researcher have in relation to the field and the people involved?

This paper stems from a research project conducted in Vietnam between 2017 and 2019 that did not initially have a historical focus. Our research involved several stages and visits to the field by members of the author team. Starting in 2017, Author One spent several months across two years visiting Vietnam and spending time in the craft villages in the North

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as well as Vietnam's major urban centres. She was joined by two other members of the team for a series of interviews and site visits in 2017, 2018 and 2019. During this period, we interviewed politicians, designers, business practitioners, educators and those living and working in the craft sector across Vietnam. However, as the research unfolded, the need to include business and organisational histories became apparent, and the role of records and archives became central to the research process through their very absence, a problem that existed since the colonial period. The funded research involved mapping the cultural and creative industries in Vietnam, namely organisations aimed at the creation, production, dissemination and preservation of goods and services that embody cultural, artistic or creative expressions (Gasparin & Quinn, 2021a, 2021b). We already had extensive experience in this task in Europe, and we naively assumed we could apply similar approaches in Vietnam. However, from the beginning, we had to navigate the intricacies of mapping in a context which (at the time of the research) was still dominated by (self) censorship and cultural policing. This created several issues for the data collection, which prevented us from deploying established historical methodologies, such as oral history, as for many of our respondents, it was challenging to feel safe enough to open up in interviews, leading us to question our approaches to safeguarding respondents. At the same time, the State control of media and discourses prevented us from conducting a rhetorical history.

In order to address these challenges our methodology included an ethical research protocol designed to collect data whilst maintaining constant awareness of the historical and political contexts within which we were working. We followed the ethical codes of conduct set out by our HEI's and funding bodies in developing our protocols and these were reviewed and approved by our then employers. The protocol was based on conducting research with integrity, meeting those professional standards, and was built on five core elements: freedom of inquiry; honesty; rigour; transparency and open communication; and care and respect.

Our interview data was collected *via* face-to-face interviews and recorded using a digital voice recorder with the presence of translators where necessary. We worked to ensure that the procedures and criteria used to identify/recruit research participants, the informed consent procedures we used for participation, and the templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets were written in language and terms intelligible to participants. In the consent sheet (in English and translated into Vietnamese), we explained what the purpose of the research was and what it was that we were seeking consent for, along with explaining exactly what would happen to the data that participants provided.

In conducting participatory research, seven principles were followed: Mutual respect; Equality and inclusion; Democratic participation; Active learning; Making a difference; Collective action; and Personal integrity. Each was designed to reassure participants of our aims in the research and respect both their wishes and the wider cultural contexts. Participants were assured that their responses would be kept confidential and anonymised prior to being reproduced and that our work was not being shared with the authorities in their locations.

In this paper, we present reflections on our efforts to construct alternative methodological approaches to developing historical accounts: an object-oriented methodological approach for business history and critical fabulations. In an object-oriented method, everyday objects become the focus of attention. We consider objects as akin to documents (Buckland, 1991), embodying a sector's knowledge extension (Buckland, 1997), and, through their relational materiality (Decker, 2014), as physical or symbolic signs representing and reconstructing memorial and conceptual phenomena (Barber & Peniston-Bird, 2009). This method leads to

insights which could otherwise not be grasped through textual documentation alone (Hood, 2009), expanding the boundaries of spaces of inquiry of historical and archival research by displaying histories through objects (Eiseman & Frenkel, 2021), creating affordances (Foroughi et al., 2024) and propensity. Indeed, objects can become means through which remembering is performed, and through them, historical narratives are created and relations formed, which could not be otherwise articulated through usual oral history approaches.

The second method, critical fabulation, was developed by Saidiya Hartman (2008). It offers a historiographical method for bringing together archival research with speculative imagination to address gaps, silences, and deletion of historical records. By using critical fabulations, we understood how the actors in the field challenged dominant narratives, and, through artistic interventions, we explored alternative perspectives that would otherwise be overlooked. We found that critical fabulations can allow business historians to reconstruct, through artistic research, possible scenarios, experiences, and networks concerning the lived realities of those underrepresented in corporate and economic archives, thereby offering a more nuanced and multidimensional understanding of the (any historical) past.

Interestingly, we found that these methods demand an engagement with the emotional dimensions of history, where economic behaviours are shaped not only by rational decision-making but also by fear, trauma, and resistance. The ethical stakes of working within politically sensitive environments, where self-censorship and state repression influence what can be remembered and spoken, also made us reflect on the need for methodological caution. Ensuring participant safety, maintaining anonymity, and co-creating interpretations with respondents where possible are essential considerations in such research.

However, as we will discuss, whilst these methods offer new ways to reconstruct business history in contexts of archival absence, they also present significant challenges. The interpretative nature of object-oriented inquiry demands sensitivity to the shifting meanings of material artefacts, as objects do not inherently 'speak' but must be situated within historical, social, and economic contexts. Hence, using a reflexive approach is important to avoid over-determining their significance or imposing anachronistic interpretations, ensuring that material evidence is read in relation to lived practices and memory, with an appreciation of the other (Decker, 2014). Similarly, the use of critical fabulation introduces the risk of over-speculation, as reconstructing erased histories requires balancing imaginative intervention with historical plausibility. While speculation is necessary to address archival silences, it must be undertaken reflexively to prevent the inadvertent reinforcing of dominant narratives or the romanticisation of historical gaps. By drawing on material culture, oral accounts, and speculative reconstruction in a way that remains transparent about the researcher's role in shaping the historical narrative, it is possible to render (any) historical reconstruction accountable to the complexities of memory, power, and absence.

The paper proceeds as follows. First, we outline some of the historical events that created contextual limitations in the research process, followed by an explanation of why established methods, such as oral history and rhetorical history were not helpful in this context. We then present one cultural and creative sector (craft) and a particular community (Hmong) as examples to elaborate our methodological innovations, explaining the two methods we used and their implementation. We conclude with a discussion and reflection on the uses and limitations of these two methods for business historians. While our empirical material centres on Vietnam's craft sector and Hmong communities, we do not aim to produce a full historical account of these contexts. Rather, we use them as an illustrative case to show *how*

these methods can be applied when traditional archives are inaccessible or politically fraught. Our focus remains on methodological innovation, using these empirical details to demonstrate the challenges and affordances of object-oriented methods and critical fabulation. Additionally, we argue that these methods enable us to trace how material practices and craft economies change meaning across historical periods, offering a dynamic rather than static view of business history in contexts of archival absence.

2. The contextual limitations: researching in the absence of archives

One of the challenges we encountered during our research was how to engage with participants to facilitate a remembering of the past in the present, given the varied ways that heritage and historical events are negotiated. Remembering is commonly viewed as ‘a complex, culturally and historically situated process and practice enacted by socially defined and emotionally charged persons in their communities of practice’ (Feldman & Feldman, 2006, p. 686). As such, remembering is a situated activity which reflects the current concerns and local problems confronted by specific memorial communities. Whilst historical narratives can be evaluated against archival sources and established interpretations, remembering is often a fluid process that invokes the past to serve present needs, shaped by social contexts and political conditions (Middleton & Edwards, 1990). Establishing the ‘accuracy’ or ‘veridicality’ of what is collectively remembered is then not a straightforward matter (Brown & Reavey, 2018). We realised that remembering, which is at the basis of some of the business history methods, such as oral history or historical narratives, can be challenging for participants in the fieldwork, either because the process of narrating the past had the potential to re-open past trauma or because they were the self-censoring to align their explanations with official histories. This section on context illustrates why archives are partial or inaccessible, underscoring the need for our methodological intervention

The interplay between control over historical narrative and cultural memory can be traced back to the colonial era. The economic advancements achieved under French colonial rule during 1887–1954 disproportionately favoured the French colonisers alongside a newly formed class of affluent Vietnamese, leaving the majority of the population disenfranchised. We provide this context to explain *why archival sources are partial, curated, and inaccessible*, justifying the need for alternative methodological approaches.

The economic divide between the colonial rulers and the Vietnamese population also created a social and cultural divide, which was reflected in the process of historical archiving and the audience for whom the archives were created. Land distribution favoured speculators and collaborators, leading to a burgeoning class of Vietnamese landlords and a surge in landless tenants subjected to exorbitant rents (Hayton, 2022). The fiscal burden imposed by the French through direct and indirect taxation, coupled with the recruitment of forced labour and exploitative conditions in mines and plantations, was the basis of the oppressive nature of colonial rule. This was exacerbated by strategies to mitigate the discontent and cover up the repression (Nguyen, 2015), as the colonial administrators implemented superficial reforms ‘aimed at misleading the masses and seducing the elites’ (p. 19).

A significant long-term legacy of French colonial activity in the region was the abolition of the Vietnamese script following a 1910 decree mandating the use of the Latin alphabet (Burlette, 2007; Nefftzger & Hébrard, 1912). This shift resulted in a dearth of accessible written records from before this date, as many documents written in Chữ Nôm, a script adapted

from Chinese ideograms, were no longer legible to later generations. The transition to Quốc Ngữ alphabet, developed by Portuguese, Italian, and French missionaries in the seventeenth century for religious translation purposes, displaced traditional Vietnamese writing, leading to the loss of vast bodies of literature and historical records (Singh, 2015), as several of these archives were either neglected, destroyed, or rendered inaccessible (Lieberman, 1993). Furthermore, since the French colonial epoch, the archives were curated by either French officials or Vietnamese elite close to the French government, reporting facts from the perspective of the colonial power (Nefftzer & Hébrard, 1912). These colonial-era tactics of narrative control persisted through successive regimes, shaping the dominant state-sanctioned histories and further marginalising alternative accounts (Singh, 2015).

The 1953–1956 Agrarian Reform in North Vietnam entrenched a culture of silence and distrust since it was based on a campaign of betrayal of friends, neighbours and family members (Vu, 2014). As part of the Communist Party's campaign to redistribute land, the government encouraged peasants to denounce landlords and so-called 'class enemies' (Dang, 2018; Rato, 2004). Some of the denunciations were motivated by personal grudges, jealousy or fear of being accused oneself. Other public denunciations were based on forced betrayals, where people were coerced into accusing one another. The accused were executed, imprisoned, or subjected to public humiliation (Tria Kerkvliet & Selden, 1998). This period of mass persecution created deep psychological scars, reinforcing a collective reluctance to discuss historical trauma openly.

This trauma was reinforced by the Vietnam war and its aftermath. During the Vietnam War (1955–1975), deep divisions emerged within families and communities that further reinforced a culture of silence around the past (Moise, 1976). During the war, friends and family members turned against each other due to ideological differences, political paranoia, and counterinsurgency operations. In the South, the Phoenix Program, led by the CIA and the South Vietnamese government (ARVN), encouraged informants to betray suspected Viet Cong supporters, resulting in wrongful imprisonments, torture, and assassinations (Valentine, 2016). Thousands of suspected Viet Cong supporters were falsely accused, and US soldiers were not able to distinguish civilians from Viet Congs (Ahern, 2010). At the same time, in North Vietnam, fear of espionage and counter-revolutionary elements led to periodic purges of suspected Western spies.

After the fall of Saigon in 1975, the communist government forced South Vietnamese officials, soldiers and intellectuals to re-education camps, which continued for several years (Duiker, 1980; Nguyen & Richey, 1982). A version of the re-education camps was still present when we did our fieldwork in 2017; we met and worked with academics who had to 'attend them' after they were reported to the police for having taught topics that were either not officially approved or they had taught them from the 'wrong' perspective. A few of the artists we interviewed were also imprisoned for displaying unauthorised material or had been subject to raids from the cultural police. One of our European colleagues had to spend one night in prison as he did not have the proper paperwork for conducting research in a particular region. These are a few examples of a unique political and social context which had significant methodological challenges. Therefore, we needed to provide additional care in our methodological approach to avoid putting respondents into unpleasant or risky situations, making them revive traumas, unduly challenging their beliefs, and overcoming the limitations of the lack of engagement of with political discourses.

Our response to the challenges posed by this extremely complex historical and memorial landscape was to consider the suitability of two initially relevant methodological approaches – oral history and rhetorical history. In the following two sections, we explain why we considered them, but also why they proved not to be suitable for this context.

Oral history is a method for directly eliciting lived experiences through spoken accounts, which positions memory as both a historical source and a dynamic social practice (Abrams, 2016; Portelli, 1991). It may also be used to capture firsthand accounts of business experiences that are missing from traditional archives (Thiessen, 2019). Oral history may focus on the memories of individuals (Hodgson, 2007; Rintamäki et al., 2023) to explore aspects such as the importance of entrepreneurial families as business actors, particular organisational forms of business groups, and relationships to globalisation and varieties of capitalism (Dávila, 2013; MacKenzie et al., 2021). It has also been used to explore the role of actors in inter-organisational learning, business-government relations and industry evolution (Popp & Fellman, 2017) and in corporate identity construction through showing how employees make sense of their work experiences through narratives about their companies (Kroeze & Vervloet, 2019).

Oral history is typically conducted through interviews specifically designed to elicit narration of the past (Decker, 2022) with individuals who participated in or witnessed particular events (Okihiro, 1981). Interviews are recorded and transcribed for posterity (Decker et al., 2021), with transcription legitimising the historicity of the source (Giacomin, 2023), its preservation (Ritchie, 2012) and the possibility for later and multiple uses. Oral history interviews are often obtained through a snowballing approach (Bailey, 2019), enabling the form of a corpus based on the aggregation of the collected memories (Olick, 1999) and other historical sources comparable to traditional written records (Giacomin, 2023). As a dynamic social practice, oral histories are often shaped by subjectivity and the relational process of narration, performance, and memory (Thomson, 2007), which inform the structure, rhythm and style of the narration and the mutual affection of past and present on the recollection (Giacomin, 2023). The social practice of collecting oral histories is, furthermore, characterised by collaboration, i.e. an active encounter between researcher and interviewee, and mutability, as the interactions contribute to informing the course of the conversation (Portelli, 2009).

Although oral histories in business history have been largely integrated into written records, it is not always possible to observe the complexity of contexts and business issues (Crawford & Bailey, 2019); hence, the epistemological and methodological potential of oral histories has been recently debated (Jones & Comunale, 2019), as in cases where archives are absent (Cruz, 2014) or may be biased because dictatorships (Favero & Gaspari, 2024) or colonialism (Decker, 2013). Jones and Comunale (2019) focused on the use of oral history in emerging markets as a method to fill the gaps left by the unavailability or incompleteness of corporate archives and to challenge conventional Western-centric theories of different economic and political conditions, contributing, in this way, to a process of decolonisation of business history methods. The potential of oral history has been demonstrated in the study of emerging markets (Crawford, 2019; Jones & Comunale, 2019; Verhoef, 2017), where colonialism, political turbulence and state intervention affected the formation of archives (Jones & Comunale, 2018). Emerging markets lack strong traditions of maintaining corporate archives, being mainly used by large corporations, leaving small business owners, minority entrepreneurs, and informal sector workers aside. This makes oral history a crucial alternative data source for business historians and, even in cases where archival records exist, they can

often prove inaccessible to researchers due to private ownership, political sensitivities, or corporate secrecy. Many emerging market economies also lack the institutional infrastructure (e.g. legal protections and market regulations), and, hence, businesses rely more on personal networks, family businesses, and informal agreements, which oral history helps document (Jones & Comunale, 2019). It has been demonstrated that companies selectively use oral histories to construct their own pasts, sometimes in ways that omit critical perspectives, particularly those of marginalised groups (Thiessen, 2019), which integrates oral history and rhetorical analysis. Hence, oral history is not a neutral recounting of facts but an active process of meaning- and sense-making (Frisch, 1990; Kroeze & Vervloet, 2019).

Despite these many potential uses, we were unable to deploy oral history in Vietnam, since control over historical narratives exercised by the state does more than simply influence how individuals remember and recount events. Fear of surveillance, repercussions, or the resurfacing of past accusations can result in deliberate self-censorship and strategic forgetfulness (Malarney, 2001). This led us to consider how respondents might navigate the risks associated with remembering and speaking openly and, in particular, how issues around historical contingencies and trauma might surface. We concluded that ethically and practically we were not properly equipped to manage the risks of triggering traumatic pasts for participants, whether due to the potential resurfacing of old accusations or the pain of reliving moments of personal loss and conflict. Furthermore, since we had ourselves experienced being censored, we did not want to put our respondents at risk. Even if the interviews were anonymised and we followed the procedure to not retain sensitive data, we were afraid that some of the respondents could have been identified anyway due to their line of work.

Another method we took into consideration was rhetorical history. *Rhetorical history* refers to the strategic use of historical narratives to shape collective memory (Anteby & Molnár, 2012), organisational identity (Suddaby et al., 2016), and social legitimacy (Foster et al., 2017; Suddaby & Greenwood, 2005), acknowledging a difference between the past as a set of occurred events and history as the recollection of the past in the present (Wilson et al., 2022). Unlike traditional historiography, which aspires to objective historical accuracy, rhetorical history acknowledges that historical narratives are actively constructed, contested, and negotiated to serve particular interests (Wadhvani et al., 2018) as, through a process of 'historical consciousness' (Suddaby, 2016), history is determinant in the definition of actors' identity and action through time (Wadhvani & Bucheli, 2014), shaping their experience of the present and their expectation for the future (Koselleck, 2004). Within this, corporate archives could be contested spaces, where different stakeholders, including owners, archivists, and historians, compete to shape the official historical narrative (Popp & Fellman, 2020).

In particular, strategic uses of the past shape and drive identity and memory work (Anteby & Molnár, 2012) by emphasising what can be remembered and what should be forgotten within and between communities (Coraiola et al., 2023), through the mobilisation of the perception of particular past events, myths, symbols (Foster et al., 2011) and material artefacts (Giovannoni & Napier, 2023). As Wadhvani et al. (2018) argue, history is performative since historical narratives actively shape organisational identity, strategy, and power relations. They emphasise that history is not just about recording the past but also about organising the present and imagining the future. As history becomes an asset that might be used strategically (Suddaby et al., 2016), imbalances in mnemonic capabilities (Coraiola & Murcia, 2019) and control over the past play a critical role in the emergence of concurrent historical narratives. In contexts where political authority is tightly linked to historical legitimacy, for

example, where a state carefully curates historical discourse to reinforce its ideological foundation, the control over the past enables the production of hegemonic historical narratives that elide, discard, and silence contradictory memories of other communities and minorities within the same environment (Aeon & Lamertz, 2021; Were, 2018). For example, official Vietnamese historiography emphasises resistance, victory, and socialist progress while strategically omitting, reframing, or marginalising events that contradict the dominant narrative. This is evident in how the agrarian reform of the 1950s, which led to mass executions and widespread suffering, and is downplayed or justified as necessary for revolutionary progress (Vu, 2019). Similarly, the complex allegiances and betrayals of the Vietnam War era are often reduced to a binary opposition between heroic revolutionaries and traitorous collaborators, overlooking the lived experiences of those caught up in the middle of the conflict (Marr, 2013).

While rhetorical history has been employed to analyse how dominant institutions manipulate historical discourse, this method also presents significant limitations, particularly in studying marginalised or suppressed perspectives (Smith & Russell, 2016; Vaara & Lamberg, 2016). Furthermore, rhetorical history has been critiqued for failing to account for a plurality of voices (Foroughi, 2020) and for struggling to deal with the organisational disruption caused by forgetting (Ciuk & Kostera, 2010). The Vietnamese diaspora, consisting of refugees, intellectuals, and artists who fled the country after 1975, could offer a crucial counterpoint to state-sponsored historical narratives. The literature has indeed shown that diasporic memory work, including oral histories, literature, and artistic expression, challenges the hegemonic control of history by foregrounding experiences of displacement, loss, and political repression (Hoskins, 2011). However, these alternative histories are often fragmented and contested, shaped by generational divides, transnational influences, and shifting political contexts (Nguyen, 2017). Moreover, their accessibility is constrained by state censorship in Vietnam, which restricts the circulation of dissenting historical accounts and criminalises engagement with politically sensitive topics (Zinoman, 2001). For example, the Gang of Five, a group of Vietnamese artists whose work critically engages with history and memory, exemplifies these tensions. While their art subtly challenges official narratives, they operate within constraints that necessitate coded symbolism and indirect critique rather than overt historical revisionism.

Ultimately, we decided against rhetorical history as an approach since we did not have access to participants from the diaspora or persons who openly had either direct or vicarious experience of different histories around Vietnam (although we did interview several Canadian or American citizens whose parents escaped Saigon by boat). We felt that without their testimony, the method would struggle to enable an analysis of the silences, omissions, and affective dimensions of history that characterise both state-controlled memories. Moreover, rhetorical history tends to privilege institutional actors, which risks reifying the power structures it seeks to critique (Greenwood et al., 2002; Smith & Russell, 2016), without challenging 'official histories' that accompany a one-party state.

Hence, researching the craft sector in the Hmong communities in the absence of archives was a challenge. We sought to resolve this by adopting two novel research strategies: analysing objects as mediators of memories and engaging in speculative fabulation. In the following sections we first provide an overview of the research setting, then present the two methodological approaches we adopted and their challenges. By combining these two approaches, we not only address archival silences but also present how objects and craft

practices have been different meanings and political functions over time, from colonial rule to socialist transformation and contemporary marketisation.

3. The research setting: the Hmong craft sector in Vietnam as methodological demonstration

This section does not aim to provide a comprehensive historical account of Hmong craft economies or Vietnamese history. Instead, it offers necessary contextual detail to show *why* conventional methods were inadequate and *how* our alternative methodological approaches were practically deployed. We foreground this case as an empirical demonstration of methodological adaptation in contexts of archival absence, self-censorship, and historical erasure. We focus on one of the creative and cultural sectors we researched: craft in the Hmong community, in the village of Sapa, Northern Vietnam. The Hmong communities living in Sapa have historically faced discrimination and marginalisation by the majority Kinh ethnic Vietnamese population and the Vietnamese government. This marginalisation stems from historical, political, and socio-economic factors rooted in Vietnam's colonial and post-colonial transformations.

During French colonial rule, the Hmong, like other ethnic minorities in the northern highlands, were largely excluded from governance and formal economic structures. French administrators placed them within the framework of ethnic classification (*montagnards* or 'hill people'), reinforcing their socio-political exclusion (Tapp, 1989). The colonial economy focused on lowland rice cultivation and rubber plantations, leaving the Hmong outside these economic networks. However, the French military and intelligence services also recruited Hmong auxiliaries, especially in border areas, for their knowledge of the terrain and skills in guerrilla warfare (Cooper, 1984). This ambiguous positioning, simultaneously marginalised and militarily useful, would shape their later experiences during the First Indochina War (1945–1954) and Vietnam/American War (1955–1975). For example, some Hmong groups sided with the French against the Việt Minh, continuing a pattern of colonial-era alliances (Nugent-Stephens & Monaghan, 2024). During the Vietnam War, many Hmong in Laos were recruited by the CIA to fight against communist forces. While it remains unclear to what extent they were coerced or participated willingly, this association with U.S. forces led to severe repercussions after the war (Nugent-Stephens & Monaghan, 2024). In Vietnam, Hmong villages accused of aiding anti-communist forces faced reprisals, and their historical role remains a sensitive issue. The absence of Hmong representation in Vietnamese national museums, such as the Women's Museum in Hanoi (at least until the last time we visited it, in 2019), reflects state narratives that exclude groups with perceived allegiances to colonial or foreign powers. Religious persecution of the Hmong was also an issue. Under French rule, Christian missionaries converted some Hmong groups to Catholicism and Protestantism. After the communist victory, these religious affiliations became grounds for repression, as independent religious groups were viewed as political threats (Ngo, 2015). Hmong Christian communities faced forced renunciations, surveillance, and occasional crackdowns, a pattern that continues today, particularly for groups practising evangelical Christianity.

Following the war, Vietnam's government sought to integrate ethnic minorities into the socialist economy through collectivisation and land reforms. However, these policies disrupted traditional Hmong agricultural practices, which were based on shifting cultivation and autonomous land management. The government's drive to standardise land use under

state control led to forced relocations and restrictions on traditional farming techniques (Dang et al., 2000). Additionally, forest conservation policies, often tied to national tourism and economic strategies, displaced Hmong communities from lands they had historically inhabited, further marginalising their economic prospects.

The Đổi Mới economic reforms of 1986 liberalised Vietnam's economy, opening new opportunities but also increasing inequalities for ethnic minorities. While urban centres and lowland agricultural sectors started to improve their economic and social conditions, the highlands remained isolated. Current touristic development of Sapa has had ambivalent effects: while some Hmong have benefitted by selling handicrafts and guided treks, these often reinforces stereotypes of the Hmong culture as exotic and backward looking (Ngo, 2015; Roberge et al., 2025), and the economic gains from the tourism in Sapa have largely favoured Kinh entrepreneurs who control land, businesses, and infrastructure, leading to further dispossession of Hmong lands (Ngo, 2015). Activist Hmong movements advocating for land rights or greater autonomy are often suppressed under the justification of maintaining national unity. A common reframing in official discourse in not providing less control connects to the need to protect communities from painful memories, such as the exposition to wartime chemicals (Singh, 2015), and the presence of landmines in the forests that are still active in some areas.

In these communities, the absence of archives is the outcome of many different processes: the absence of records due to the oral culture and the rural areas, destruction or decay, or silence and secrecy. The Hmong communities experienced their historical narratives being marginalised, fragmented, or mediated through external perspectives. The Hmong, as a transnational ethnic group spanning Southeast Asia (Praphan, 2024) (and beyond) have historically maintained their own oral traditions, artistic expressions, and ritual practices as primary forms of knowledge transmission (Berry & Cole, 2011; Roberge et al., 2025). Hence, their history has been predominantly written by outsiders, such as colonial administrators, missionaries, and state officials, who framed them within the dominant national or geopolitical agendas. These latter are typically rooted in anthropocentrism, prioritising human agency whilst marginalising the roles of spirits, ancestors, and sacred landscapes, which are pivotal features of Hmong cultural memory and historical narratives. This human-centric approach taken in historical records can render invisible spiritual and religious experiences and negate their role in establishing meaningful relationships between past and present. Recognising this interconnectedness with the business history of the craft sector requires thinking beyond established (Western) ontological division and recognising animist cosmologies as intrinsic to local organisational practices. Hmong cosmology does not make a sharp distinction between the human and spiritual realms: ancestral spirits, nature spirits, and shamans mediate between worlds, influencing health, decision-making, and social order. Rituals such as spirit-calling ceremonies, divination, and shamanic healing serve as forms of knowledge transmission, linking past, present, and future through interactions with the unseen. The Hmong story cloths (*paj ntaub*), for example, illustrate historical events not as linear progressions but as fluid, interconnected memories, with spirits featured in sacred places. Hence, in our research, we realised that the analysis of historical narratives around craft then needs to find a way of including these actors along human subjects.

In the following sections, we present how we approached these challenges through object-oriented method and critical fabulation.

4. Objects as mediators of history and memory: an object-oriented method for business history

Object-oriented method is drawn from approaches to social remembering (Middleton & Brown, 2005) and material engagement (Prezioso & Alessandrini, 2023). In this literature, objects are treated as focal points for debating, contesting and reinterpreting memory. Maurice Halbwachs (1980, 1992) coined the term 'collective memory' and described how communities 'engrave' memory into objects and places. He argued that groups 'cut up space in order to compose, either definitively or in accordance with set methods, a fixed framework within to enclose and retrieve its remembrances' (Halbwachs, 1980, p. 157). An individual object is then a gateway into a network of spatially emplaced relations that hold together a collective framework of memory. The material structure of the object, i.e. the way it looks, smells, responds to touch and sits within the local environment, then 'mediates' and 'lends sense' to what is being remembered (Reavey & Brown, 2009). But objects can also serve as points of contestation around which debate and controversy about the past and its contemporary meaning and relevance can unfold (Allen & Brown, 2016).

Objects are powerful means through which a relationship to the past can be mediated (Middleton & Brown, 2005), and explain 'with whom we remember and how we do so' (Eisenman & Frenkel, 2021, p. 1). This is clearly the case with objects that are already endowed with memorial significance, such as a family heirloom, a piece of clothing worn on special occasions, or a functional object like an old tool or utensil that carries with it a sense of 'times past'. But mundane objects can also act as signs or prompts of memories that are otherwise unspeakable. For example, Brown et al. (2013) analyse how objects such as clothing and toys act as ambiguous mediators in the difficult relationship between adoptive parents and adopted children. These objects have a 'spectral' quality where they are imbued with potential memories of events from the early life of the child, such as neglect or trauma, which may be 'unspoken' until such time as the child is emotionally equipped to be able to engage with them. In this way 'objects do not offer a simply gateway to the past. Their power to link past and present comes from the contingent and situated manner in which they are encountered in acts of remembering' (Brown et al., 2013, p. 181). Prezioso and Alessandrini (2023) similarly argue that things become meaningful due to 'their material qualities, their participation in instances of material engagement and the sociocultural settings of which they are part' (p. 970). An object-oriented approach focuses on exploring objects as gateways into a web of memorial relations. However, since objects do not 'speak for themselves', we adopted a process that allowed reflexivity, by: (i) identifying relevant objects; (ii) using these object as an invitation to storytelling; (iii) analysing the political and historical dimensions narrated in these object stories and (iv) re-establishing the contemporary socioeconomic context. We illustrate these steps in the next sub-sections, providing examples from the fieldwork.

4.1. Identifying and contextualising objects and place

Sapa is well-known for its ethnic minority communities, including the Hmong and Red Dao, who rely on craft-based economies rooted in traditional knowledge. In July 2017, author 1 attended a seminar on social enterprises, organised by a foreign NGO. Many young Hmong and Red Dao took part in the event. After the seminar, the group visited a Red Dao village and spent the afternoon visiting the facilities of a local social enterprise, including guest houses, traditional bath cabins, and places where oils were produced for massages, made using the historical knowledge held tacitly by the old women of the village (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Traditional landscape Hmong village: rice cultivation and forests.

In traditional Hmong villages, shared bathhouses or communal bathing areas can be decades or even centuries old. The communal bathing tradition has a long cultural and organisational meaning, based on oral transmission of herbal medicinal knowledge (Whitney et al., 2016). However, this knowledge has been threatened by deforestation and state land policies (Dang et al., 2012): since the 1980s, the Vietnamese state has conducted an aggressive policy of forest management for industrial reasons, burning down the forests to replace them with cultivation of commercial woods for international trade. These activities, coupled with massive construction work, are compromising the fragile ecosystem around Hmong communities. What used to be 'common knowledge' until the reunification is now carried by few community members who know the specific properties of local plants (Figure 2).

The group decided to take a bath. Women were bathing inside and men outside (in streams or makeshift wooden enclosures). In the Hmong highlands, bathing is more than an act of hygiene: it is a ritual, a moment of gathering and sharing stories. Hmong women come here after a tiring workday in the fields. Hmong is a patriarchal society (Dang et al., 2000), where women carry out most of the agricultural work (such as growing rice), attending the water buffalo and taking care of the household, while men spend most of the day at the local bar drinking rice wine and playing board games. The women usually arrived here tired, and, as they explained, the bath was a space of both restoration and connection, a pause between work in the fields and work at home. The shared bathhouse was a space of reciprocity, care and community. In the female baths, elders passed down wisdom, teaching the young how to mix medicinal leaves to ease sore muscles, and how to recognise the plants that heal and those that harm them. They also discussed cupping techniques, a practice made using heated glass or bamboo cups that are placed on the back or shoulders, and with a piece of burning cotton or herbal-infused flame placed inside the cup to create a vacuum. The vacuum sucks up the skin, facilitating blood flow and drawing out toxins. After a few minutes, the cup is removed, sometimes followed by a massage using herbal balms or oils to enhance relaxation. For this reason, the technique often leaves circular marks on the skin (which fade after a few days) due to the suction drawing blood closer to the surface.

Figure 2. Bath house.

Figure 3. Herbal preparation.

The first time that (Author 1) saw the foreheads of a Hmong woman, she/he thought she had an accident. The translator explained that this technique helps with body aches, colds, and general fatigue, which are often linked to hard labour in agricultural settings. For the Hmong this is both a healing tradition and a form of spiritual cleansing which balances the body's internal energies (Figure 3).

This entry into cultural memory around craft intrigued us to explore the significance of artefacts related to the cultivation and management of local plants, and their connection with craft. Conversation with the local women indicated that the flux of energies, spirits and the lives of plants in the forest are constitutive of the organisation of the Hmong knowledge and the economic and cultural practices, including craft. However, these practices have been dismissed by official Vietnamese medical practices and are further threatened by the challenge of changing national agricultural policy and the marginalisation of the community. This bathhouse then is an example of a (hidden) gateway into memory concerning the community's economic and social organisation.

4.2. Mobilising objects to elicit stories

The context provided by the bathhouse indicated that there could be value in shifting conversations towards objects rather than events. Almost all the agricultural and craft related objects used by the ethnic minorities are ‘historical’. Whilst they have been transformed and adapted over time, they have not been replaced with automatic machines. The communities use the term ‘daily-life’ objects rather than ‘traditional’ artefacts. The notion of ‘traditional clothes’ and ‘traditional tools’ is derived from and imposed by the tourism industry and does not have any meaning for Indigenous people. Daily-life objects are mundane, silent and taken-for-granted but at the same time a vital part of their lived experience, a techné that can serve as a mnemonic affordance (Foroughi et al., 2024) in the craft activities, reinforcing the conceptual ties between collective memory and the social construction of craft communities.

Author 1, accompanied by a translator and the local guide, went for lunch in a large guesthouse whose family owners cultivated rice in addition to running the establishment. There were a few baskets, resembling backpack carriers, resting against the wall. They were made of bamboo frames, darkened by time and usage, and their straps frayed a little by years of wear. The basket is called *lub tawb*, shaped to fit the body and designed for endurance. It is used to carry firewood, rice, maize, medicinal herbs, and even babies (Figure 4).

The owner of the place, a woman whose hands were rough from years of farming, lifted the basket onto her back and shifted the strap across her forehead to show how it worked. ‘This one belonged to my mother’, she said. ‘She used it to carry rice from the terraces. Now, I use it for vegetables and firewood’. This passing down of objects through generations is not uncommon. In the village, every household had baskets of different sizes, some newly woven, others repaired over decades. The woman recollected how the grandmother used the basket during the war to hold supplies, hide children, and even transport the wounded when the roads were too dangerous to use. ‘At night, we ran with whatever we could carry’, an elder recalled, pointing to an old basket reinforced with fresh bamboo strips. ‘This one has seen more than rice fields’. This provided the opportunity to explore with them the organisation and use of agrarian lands, a topic that would otherwise have been highly sensitive. She explained the activities she did during the war, how it affected her family, and

Figure 4. Baskets in use in daily activities.

some of the fears in going around the forest with the basket. Although Sapa was not heavily bombed like Laos or central Vietnam, some areas still have unexploded ordnances. 'We tell the children, don't dig too deep in some places,' she said, gesturing towards a stretch of forest that has not been cleaned, as bombs might still be there. Over the years, there had been accounts of human and livestock injuries and occasional discoveries of rusted shells buried just below the surface. The conversation then shifted to trade practices. Once, the baskets had only circulated within the village, but now they were being sold to visitors as 'traditional crafts'. A woman laughed as she explained: 'The tourists want them to look in a certain way to be brought home. But we don't make baskets for decoration. We make them to last'. What had been a practical necessity was now being repurposed as a historical trinket, an object to be admired rather than a tool to be used. However, the community had decided to adapt to the new demand and weave more baskets for tourist souvenirs, in parallel with maintaining them as working objects.

4.3. Analysing political and historical dimensions of objects

In the second stage of the fieldwork, Author 1 returned to Sapa during the winter. It was humid and cold, with no central heating in the houses, only open fires. She was hosted in a guest house attached to a social enterprise in a Hmong craft workshop. There were no walls on the front nor the back of the workshop, resulting in a feeling of being constantly cold. The workshop smelled of burned wood, damp fabric, and herbal dyes, but also delicious food that was served for breakfast and lunch.

Author 1 came here to further understand textile craft—not merely the mechanics of dyeing and weaving but the rhythms of creation, the history of the textile, its politics, and its continuation across time. Studying a newly dyed textile, Author 1's fingers traced a recurring cross-like pattern on the fabric. 'Is this meant to be a religious symbol?' they asked their translator. The artisans looked at them, amused, and shook her head. 'No, this represents the fields,' she said. 'The motif reflects an agricultural cycle, a way to put Hmong farming knowledge on the fabric. In this way,' the translator continued, 'knowledge is passed down not through books but through fabrics and stitches' (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Fabric patterns and design.

Author 1 apologised, explaining that in Western culture, the cross is often a religious symbol. The local guide continued: 'There are religious symbols, but not in the way you think', she said. 'Hmong people believe in the spirits of nature'. The conversation shifted, and suddenly, the fabric was no longer just an aesthetic object; it became a site of historical tension, a material record of the struggles over identity, faith, and survival that had shaped the Hmong experience. 'When the French were here, they converted many Hmong to Christianity', she said, nodding towards the town centre. 'There is a church there, have you seen it?' The presence of that church was a religious landmark remnant of French colonial time (1887–1954). During that period, there were forced and voluntary conversions to Catholicism under colonial authority. Conversion to Christianity was not just a question of faith, it became entangled with political and military alliances. Many Hmong Christians had fought alongside the French against the Viet Minh in the First Indochina War (1945–1954), leading to violent reprisals from anti-colonial forces. Religious affiliation became a political liability. After the colonial period, to be Hmong and Christian was to risk suspicion of being regarded as a collaborator, an enemy of the revolution. This tension continued within the Communist state.

During the period when the fieldwork was conducted, ethnic diversity was officially recognised but strictly defined, and practices that could be preserved and marketed as 'traditional heritage' were centrally defined. The translator indicated as an example the Fansipan Mountain, the highest mountain in the region, which was a sacred pilgrimage site for the Hmong. Until a few years before, this mountain could be visited only on foot. But, since the tourism ministry authorised the construction of a cable car, it was now readily accessible to all. In the valley, historical, natural, ecological and heritage buildings were gradually being replaced by modern hotels and other commercial structures to accommodate visitor growth, inevitably changing community life. 'Lately, there is less time for crafting and less availability of raw material for making craft, for example', the local guide commented. Moreover, the representations of craft activities changed to accommodate the imaginaries of increased touristic fluxes, transforming the cloth from a site of knowledge and historical narratives into an exotic artefact for tourists (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Examples of the use of Hmong craft in tourist venues.

An object-oriented method here allowed an understanding of historical and socio-economic transformations, focusing on the materiality of objects, such as textiles, as active participants in historical and social processes. The hands-on engagement with craft allowed for an experiential mode of inquiry that elicited insights beyond what was articulated in interviews, including shifting politics of material culture, as the meanings of textiles were renegotiated in response to colonial histories, state policies, and the pressures of tourism. This approach illuminated how the very fabric of Hmong life, in this case literally and metaphorically, was being woven into new configurations of economic and political power.

4.4. Re-establishing the current socioeconomic context

As Author 1 walked through a craft market, the contrast between the locally handmade textiles (Figure 7a) and the mass-manufactured (Figure 7b) clothes and souvenirs was quite visible. A group of Red Dao (another ethnic minority of Sapa) women approached, wrapped in black capes embroidered with geometric patterns, their heads covered in red scarves, symbolising their transition into marriage. They displayed their crafts: small bracelets, wallets, and bags, each offered for 100,000 dong (€4). At first glance, these objects fit within the broader globalised handicraft market, where cultural symbols are transformed into portable, affordable commodities. Yet, as Author 1 discussed with the translator and local guide, some of the items were not handmade but factory-produced imitations. 'Made in China', Author 1 commented, holding up a bag. Her translator shook her head. 'Yes, possibly made by Hmong workers in Chinese factories', she clarified. She said that there were several Hmong workers in China, mostly working in factories producing cheap mass production of Hmong-inspired crafts. Some of the factories were just across the border, so some workers commuted with scooters. However, there was also a dark side to this mobility: the trafficking of young women. 'Some girls here disappear', she said whispering. 'They are taken across the border to China'. Some young Hmong girls were kidnapped after being lured into fake marriages, with the prospect of a rich life in the city. However, according to the translator, there was a consensus among the Hmong that the government was downplaying the number of girls that were kidnapped and the seriousness of the allegations due to ethnic conflicts. This was not a conversation that would likely have happened outside of the very specific context of discussing the objects at hand (Figure 8).

Holding the bracelet, Author 1 further discussed the difference between doing craft for the community use versus for tourists. One lady said that she saw craft for tourists as

Figure 7. (a,b) Sapa market, with stands that sell factory-made craft.

Figure 8. Market with hand-made craft.

a possibility to earn money on top of agricultural labour, hoping that her children would choose to attend the university and move to Hanoi for a 'better future'. Others, like my Hmong tour guide, a 19-year-old woman, the first from her village to go to university, said she would return home after she concluded university. 'I love my land, I love my people', she explained. 'I want tourists to appreciate our craft, not just buy it. I want to build something sustainable for us'.

What emerged from these conversations was a tension between various community histories, the willingness to protect them and their economic organisation, but at the same time interest in opening to economic change. The mass production of craft objects for tourists and global markets threatened the uniqueness of traditional techniques, but at the same time, they were seen as new possibilities for economic independence, education, and cultural exchange.

4.5. Challenges and limitations of the object-oriented method

While the object-oriented approach enabled us to access silenced or unspeakable histories, applying it in practice posed significant challenges. First, objects do not inherently 'speak' or carry stable meanings. Their significance is contingent on context, relationships, and interpretation. This required us to be reflexive and cautious about not imposing our own assumptions or over-determining meanings for the participants. Second, conversations prompted by objects sometimes veered into sensitive or traumatic territory, demanding careful ethical management to avoid re-traumatizing respondents or creating risk in politically controlled environments. Finally, this method can produce fragmentary or partial insights, which resist easy systematisation. While this is a strength in terms of acknowledging complexity, it complicates efforts to construct coherent historical narratives for business history.

5. Critical fabulation: a methodological approach for business history

We employed critical fabulation (Hartman, 2008) as a method to mobilise storytelling and speculative narratives to bridge historical gaps, address omissions, and give voice to forgotten or marginalised communities. Critical fabulation merges material from historical or archival analysis with speculative storytelling, allowing for a reimagining of past events through a creative and critical lens. As Hartman (2008) suggests, the resulting critical fabulations can challenge dominant historiographical narratives by exploring not just what is documented but also what might have been omitted or obscured, including forgotten voices, emphasising memory as a living, dynamic entity rather than a fixed historical record. This approach moves beyond the constraints of uneven empirical data and contestations around factual accuracy to propose alternative histories that blend documented events with speculative possibilities. It seeks to recover marginalised voices and perspectives by reimagining historical events through a critical lens, offering alternative histories and narratives, particularly for communities that have been systematically excluded from dominant accounts (Best, 2011; Klein, 2013; Meliande, 2024).

This method falls under the umbrella of creative practice as a mode of inquiry (Hjorth et al., 2020), which aims to include the experiential dimensions of knowledge that are otherwise rendered silent within oral and textual communication (Niedderer & Roworth-Stokes, 2007). Thus, creative practices offer new ways to reflect on and about methods and practices of research by making mundane and tacit social practices critically visible (Hjorth et al., 2020). Speculative approaches challenge the hegemonic dominance of scientific and economic perspectives over traditional and Indigenous ways of knowing, proposing alternatives to existing frameworks and power structures, but at the same time, researchers need to be reflexive to critically assess their positionality and the unconscious bias of treating actors as 'exotic others' (Chamat Garcés, 2025). Adopting a speculative approach does not entail replacing truth with fiction, but rather embracing a multilayered, complex approach (Gasparin et al., 2025), challenging the static nature of historical records and advocating for a more inclusive and participatory engagement with the past.

For us, critical fabulation has been an interesting approach to working with participants in the absence of archives, in the presence of self-censorship, and in raising ethical concerns for using other methods due to the potential of creating traumas. We chose to engage with a group of Vietnamese artists to perform this process, as we were aware of our positionality as Western researchers in the field. We reasoned that engaging with Vietnamese artists who already had a relationship with ethnic minorities could result in a better translation of the values and narratives of their oral culture. We approached the process of critical fabulation by asking the artists to reflect on how history could shape the understanding of organisational and societal transformations in these regions (see Vaara & Lamberg, 2016). The outcome of this process was an exhibition shown in London and Hanoi in 2019 and 2020. It consisted of two main elements: an interpretation of an indigo vat and a sensorial room with music, videos and texts written with a new typography.

5.1. Establishing the narrative framework

The methodological process began by collaborating with Vietnamese artists and a curator to define the exhibition's core narrative. The Biennale of London, where we planned to

first exhibit, proposed the theme of the 'emotional state of Vietnam'. Through discussions with artists, we chose to explore emotions among the Hmong communities, because they are shaped by historical trauma, cultural norms of restraint, and collective memory. Through this process, we found that emotions can serve as an alternative historical archive, marking out historical silences. Fear, grief, or reluctance to speak can point towards events erased from formal records but which still persist as embodied memories. We experienced during the interviews that entrepreneurs and artisans often avoided discussing past injustices that shaped their industries due to fear of repercussions, with speakers consciously or unconsciously aligning their narratives with state-sanctioned versions of history. Further, we realised that emotions also serve as forms of resistance. Silence, grief, or even humour are forms of expression that subtly reject dominant narratives and preserve alternative histories. We reflected that these were interesting markers for business history because they revealed hidden economies of care, solidarity, and survival that are often absent from official records. For example, the indigo vat that is central to craft dyeing practices serves as both a site of economic production and an emotional archive, embedding memories, social bonds, and histories of resilience within the craft-making process. Similarly, the reconstruction of the Vietnamese alphabet that one of the artists did for the exhibition represents an act of emotional and political resistance, reclaiming historical scripts lost to colonial linguistic reforms. In this way, emotional experiences can become historical artefacts, informing the narrative strategies of critical fabulation.

After establishing the core narrative, we examined the historical and cultural factors influencing emotional expression in Vietnam. Confucian principles, which emphasise harmony, hierarchy, and emotional control, have long underpinned Vietnamese social organisation (Whitmore, 1984). Emotional expression, particularly of negative emotions like anger or frustration, is often discouraged as it is seen as disruptive to group cohesion and social harmony. Open discussions of emotions are avoided to prevent personal feelings from overshadowing communal obligations. This cultural framework prioritises interpersonal harmony over individual emotional needs. The Vietnam/American War left a profound imprint on the collective psyche, fostering a norm of emotional resilience and silence. Many individuals who lived through the war or its aftermath struggle to articulate their emotions, since endurance without complaint has become an ingrained cultural value. This history of trauma, combined with Confucian ideals of restraint, creates an environment in which discussing and expressing emotions remains complex and often avoided. We also took note that gender dynamics further complicate emotional expression. The museums in Vietnam represent women as resilient. However, the artists we collaborated with researched how traditional gender roles impose strict expectations of emotional restraint, particularly for women. In Vietnamese culture, women are expected to embody patience, humility, and self-control, further limiting their ability to express emotions openly. Emotions deemed too intense or inappropriate are often suppressed in public or formal settings to maintain social decorum. This expectation extends into family life, where emotional expression may be muted to avoid conflict or embarrassment.

5.2. Materialising emotions

The artists explored emotional expression through craft. Our focus narrowed to the Hmong community's craft practices, particularly indigo dyeing, which is not merely a technique but a ritualised act of memory, emotion, and labour. Each stage, from finding indigo to dyeing

textiles, is a communal process, a moment of sharing emotions and fears, reinforcing the intricate relationship between craft, identity, and emotions.

Vietnam's business history has a longstanding artisanal tradition, spanning pottery, silk weaving, lacquerware, and wood carving. For generations, craft villages functioned as economic and cultural hubs, passing down skills and knowledge within families and communities. However, the Đổi Mới reforms of the 1980s introduced economic liberalisation and international trade, which reshaped Vietnam's craft sector. While new opportunities emerged, traditional practices were increasingly commercialised, mass-produced, or altered to meet global demand. These transformations particularly affected the Hmong community, whose crafts, once embedded in spirituality, communal labour, and ecological rhythms, became commodities tailored for the tourist and export markets. The shift from local, slow production to market-driven production disrupted the social and emotional fabric of the craft villages, threatening the history from which they originated.

The artists sought to represent craft not as an object of consumption but as an experience of creation, emphasising its meditative, collective and embodied dimensions. The indigo vat was designed to represent it as a symbol within the exhibition, transcending its function as a dyeing tool to become, instead, also a site of social exchange, storytelling, and historical resistance. Around the vat, Hmong women gathered, sharing secrets and experiences as they stirred the blue liquid, their movements bridging past and present. The rhythmic nature of weaving, carving, and dyeing provided a space to navigate patriarchal constraints and domestic responsibilities was captured in the alchemist Petri dishes ([Figure 9](#)).

The exhibition expanded beyond craft to explore broader histories of cultural loss and resilience, particularly through an artistic investigation of Vietnam's linguistic history. One artist focused on the emotional transition from Chữ Nôm (traditional Vietnamese script) to Quốc Ngữ (Latin-based script), which we discussed in [Section 2](#). He felt there had been a linguistic erasure as part of Vietnam's broader colonial and cultural transformations, and he decided to design a new typeface that reimagined lost Vietnamese scripts, blending past and present to challenge the hegemony of linguistic imperialism. This part of the exhibition was based on a year-long project of gathering evidence and finding traces in old buildings that were destroyed to remake urban space. Like the craft-based practices explored in the

Figure 9. Indigo vat and details of its Petri dishes.

exhibition, this typographic intervention served as a mode of resistance, reclaiming historical narratives that had been suppressed or reconfigured to align with colonial or state-sanctioned histories. As the indigo vat embodied a space where craftworkers encoded social, emotional, and historical knowledge into textiles, the act of reclaiming typography became a form of archival reconstruction, offering an alternative way to materialise memory and cultural identity, reflecting on the impact of economic forces (e.g. destruction of old buildings to build new skyscrapers), and on ideological and epistemic shifts (Figure 10).

5.3. Challenges and limitations of critical fabulation

The use of critical fabulation offered a creative methodology to address archival silences, but it also came with important limitations. Speculative reconstruction risks blurring the line between historical plausibility and fiction, raising questions about accuracy and legitimacy. We had to remain vigilant about avoiding romanticisation or exoticisation of the communities we worked with. Collaborating with local artists helped mitigate this risk by grounding the work in locally meaningful forms, but it also introduced new interpretive layers that required negotiation and trust. Another challenge was navigating power dynamics inherent in our role as foreign researchers facilitating this process. We found that critical fabulation demands ongoing reflexivity about positionality, accountability to participants, and transparency about the speculative nature of the interpretations produced. These limitations highlight the need for a careful ethical use of this method in business history.

6. Discussion: towards a more inclusive business history

This paper proposes a methodological contribution to business history by demonstrating how object-oriented inquiry and critical fabulation can be used to reconstruct histories in

Figure 10. Typography details of the sensorial room of the exhibition.

contexts where archives are absent, inaccessible, or politically controlled. We engaged with material culture, speculative storytelling, and emotional histories to recover silenced narratives and reveal economic and social transformations that would otherwise remain invisible. Whilst our paper includes rich empirical detail, this is not intended as a complete historiographical account of Hmong craft or Vietnamese political history. Instead, these details serve as methodological evidence, showing *how* object-oriented inquiry and critical fabulation can operate as tools for business historians to access silenced or inaccessible histories.

Our findings show that these methods are not only useful in retrieving lost histories but also in challenging dominant historiographical conventions that privilege textual documentation over embodied, material, and speculative forms of historical reconstruction. We argue that object-oriented methods and critical fabulation expand the epistemological scope of business history by moving beyond the assumption that economic histories must be derived from written records, firm archives, and government documentation (Wadhvani & Bucheli, 2014). In contexts where state-controlled historiography has shaped the dominant narrative, as in Vietnam, we realised that the reliance on textual sources risks reproducing the very silences it seeks to overcome (Zinoman, 2001). Instead, we experimented with new methods to treat material artefacts, such as textiles, agricultural tools, and craft objects as 'historical witnesses'. We found that objects function not only as economic instruments but also as sites of memory and affect, shaping intergenerational knowledge in ways that textual sources cannot fully capture (Brown et al., 2013).

Critical fabulation, in turn, enables engagement with the speculative dimensions of history, where archival gaps and silences themselves become sites of inquiry. Hartman's (2008) approach to historical reconstruction challenges the notion that history can (or should) only be written from verifiable sources, instead arguing that imaginative interventions can illuminate the lived experiences of those excluded from dominant narratives. In business history, this speculative element is particularly valuable in revealing suppressed economic contributions, alternative market formations, and overlooked labour histories (Decker, 2013; Jones & Comunale, 2019). Our study demonstrates how this method enables a nuanced discussion on craft economy in an ethnic minority through the use of emotions as research markers, where economic practices have been shaped by repression, displacement, and adaptation to shifting political economies.

A crucial question that arises from this study is whether these methods apply across all historical periods or whether they are more suited to specific temporal contexts. Our findings indicate that object-oriented methods and critical fabulations can be deployed across multiple historical periods, though their application varies depending on the nature of historical silences. Under French colonial rule (1887–1954), for instance, economic and cultural histories were curated to reflect colonial interests, erasing Indigenous trade networks and labour structures (Nguyen, 2017). Here, material culture serves as a counter-archive, allowing for the reconstruction of suppressed histories, such as the agricultural knowledge embedded in Hmong textiles (Hoskins, 2011). In contrast, during the Vietnam/American War (1955–1975), political upheaval disrupted business structures and labour markets, while state historiography actively reconfigured narratives to align with ideological objectives (Taylor, 2001). With regard to this period, the object-oriented method allowed us to trace economic adaptations through material remains, while critical fabulation provided a means to reimagine economic actors' lived experiences that are absent from official accounts. In the post-socialist transition (1986–present), where Vietnam's Đổi Mới reforms introduced economic liberalisation while reinforcing state control over historical

narratives, critical fabulation enables us to explore how economic actors navigate state censorship and global markets (Greenwood et al., 2002).

Another interesting finding is that business history can follow an emotional investigation, shaped not only by economic decisions but also by the affective dimensions of memory, trauma, and resilience. Traditional historiography tends to emphasise rational economic actors making strategic decisions based on market conditions. However, our work suggests that emotions, such as fear, silence, grief, and endurance, can play a crucial role in shaping business behaviour, particularly in politically fraught contexts. Fear, for instance, influences how individuals remember and recount economic histories. Self-censorship is not merely a methodological challenge but a historical phenomenon in itself, shaping the ways in which economic actors negotiate their past. Craftwork, too, emerges as an emotional archive, encoding memories of displacement, survival, and adaptation. Indigo dyeing and textile production, for example, are not only economic activities but also rituals of remembering and healing (Prezioso & Alessandroni, 2023). Women's labour in these industries carries an emotional weight, balancing economic survival with cultural preservation, while simultaneously resisting state-imposed narratives of heritage and authenticity. Furthermore, this raises critical epistemological questions about historical truth and multiplicity. Conventional historiography often assumes an objective past that can be reconstructed through archival research. However, historical memory in business can be mediated by power, ideology, and selective remembering (Wilson et al., 2022).

These insights lead us to reconsider dominant understandings of Hmong craft economic history. Official historiography tends to emphasise state-led industrialisation and economic modernisation, often overlooking the role of informal economies, ethnic minority craft industries, and gendered labour in shaping economic transformations. By investigating the experiences of marginalised economic actors, we show a more nuanced picture of business history, one in which informal labour, indigenous knowledge systems, and alternative economies play a central role. The history of Hmong craft sector, for example, is not a linear progression from traditional to modern production but a contested site where economic survival strategies intersect with political constraints and market forces. The commodification of Hmong crafts for tourism illustrates this dynamic, where local producers navigate state-approved heritage narratives while maintaining economic autonomy (Foster et al., 2017).

While these methodological innovations offer new ways to reconstruct business history, they are not without limitations. Object-oriented inquiry requires careful interpretation, as objects do not 'speak' in a straightforward manner; their meanings shift over time and across social contexts (Brown et al., 2013). Researchers need to critically engage with material culture to avoid imposing anachronistic or reductive interpretations. Critical fabulation, meanwhile, carries the risk of over-speculation. While it allows for the reconstruction of erased histories, there is a fine line between historical reconstruction and fictionalisation (Hartman, 2008). To mitigate these risks, we remained reflexive in our interpretative processes, recognising that these methods involve some degree of subjectivity. Nevertheless, critical fabulation embraces subjectivity as an analytical strength rather than a weakness. Instead of attempting to reconstruct a single, objective truth, this method foregrounds the interpretive agency of historians and research participants, recognising that history is always constructed through narratives, memory, and power relations. Furthermore, engaging with politically sensitive histories poses ethical challenges, these methods ensure participant safety and avoid unintended consequences for those involved in our research (Marr, 1991; Vu, 2019), by speaking through objects or having their voices mediated by the artists. Hence, for future research, we suggest that ethical considerations

should remain at the forefront of methodological innovation, ensuring that historical reconstruction does not come at the expense of those whose histories we seek to recover.

Future research should continue to explore the potential of material culture and speculative storytelling in business history, particularly in contexts where economic actors have been marginalised or erased from official narratives. For example, the integration of digital humanities tools, such as 3D modelling and AI-assisted text analysis, could further expand the possibilities for reconstructing lost economic histories. Comparative studies might also examine how object-oriented methods can be used in other postcolonial contexts to recover suppressed business histories. Additionally, speculative methodologies could be applied beyond historical reconstruction to analyse contemporary business phenomena, particularly in industries affected by economic censorship, intellectual property struggles, and contested historical narratives.

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Notes on contributors

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